

The Effects of Romantic Relationships on the Academic Performance of Twelve Graders in
Dakar

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ABSTRACT

This study is aimed at determining the effects of romantic relationships on the academic performance of twelve graders in Dakar. This study was conducted to determine whether or not there is a relationship between academic performance and motivation, time management in studying, and time spent with their partners. Specifically, it will address the following questions: (1) What percentage of twelve graders in Dakar are involved in romantic relationships? (2) What is the level of academic performance of these students? And is there a significant relationship between their romantic relationships and their academic performance? The variables were investigated using a descriptive survey method with the aid of a questionnaire. The data were then subjected to a Pearson Product Moment Correlation and a T-test. It was found out that the students' time management of the students was imbalanced, which entails that they were more focused on their romantic relationship than on studying. Time spent with the partner was found to be significantly related to academic performance. However, since the results revealed that high school students who were involved in a relationship (during the academic year 2019-2020) have a lower motivation level as students, the researcher concluded that time spent with the partner have the most significant effect on their academic performance. It is recommended that a parallel study be conducted with larger samples since the study is limited to twelve students only.

Keywords: Romantic Relationship, Academic Performance, 12 graders, Dakar.

The Effects of Romantic Relationships on the Academic Performance of 12graders in Dakar.

Background Information

“You know you are in love when you cannot fall asleep because reality is finally better than your dreams.” Dating during twelfth grade can be described as peaceful, overrated, good, bad, and distracting, and sometimes some teenagers would often describe it as a blessing depending on the type of relationship. Twelfth graders have become interested and involved in dating because of the desire to belong to one another. As a result, it is clear that over time, romantic relationships gain importance. It is often believed that romantic relationships may negatively affect adolescents’ academic outcomes because the time spent with a romantic partner might distract one from schoolwork. This research discusses the effects of the academic achievements of twelve graders on their romantic relationship. After all, according to Carroll Bryant, “Love is a two-way street constantly under construction”.

Statement of the problem. When it comes to twelfth graders, having a romantic relationship is common among many other things, and as being attracted to the other is normal, having a burden or a relationship not only in your life but also in your time may affect someone’s studies. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the students in terms of their average scores in school before, during, and after their involvement in romantic relationships?
2. What is the time management of the students in studying and with their partners?

3. Is there a significant relationship between academic performance and time management among the students?

Objectives of the study. The main objective of the study was to determine the effects of romantic relationships on the academic performance of twelfth graders in Dakar during the 2019-2020 academic year. This research paper also aims to: determine how guided the students are when it comes to this issue, and identify the key on how to manage between studies and relationships.

Discussion of hypothesis. As the need for acceptance into peer groups, which compels these students to get involved in romantic relationships for social approval or acceptance, is rapidly increasing, having a commitment to a relationship while studying may result in students getting distracted in a negative way; on the other hand, it may lead to success. Somehow, students are getting careless about making decisions on this topic.

Review of related literature. The effects of romantic relationships have long been ignored by the society we live in, whether a child or an adult; the effects vary. They may be short term or long term. Before going into the main variables of the study, the researchers discuss in the first part why adolescents get involved in romantic relationships and how these relationships contribute to the growth and development of adolescents. In the next part, the researchers talk about the connection between the independent variables in this study, such as romantic relationships, which involve time, motivation, and anxiety. These three variables were carefully examined to determine or see if there is any relationship between romantic relationships and individuals' academic performance and their effect. In the last part of the chapter, the researchers try to evaluate previous studies related to the topic of this study. Biology

has identified three basic parts of love, each driven by a unique blend of brain chemicals. Lust is governed by both estrogen and testosterone in both men and women. The attraction is driven by adrenaline, dopamine, and serotonin—the same chemicals that are released by exciting, novel experiences. As stated by Crissey (2006) in her study about the impact of romantic relationships on high school girls, there is really a challenge in “balancing romantic relationships and academic performance” in a teenager’s life. It creates pressure on how to maintain the romantic side while the academic works as well. She also pointed out that there is more than the pressure someone will feel if there is competition inside the classroom for academic awards at the end of the school year. Crissey (2006) then added that having a romantic affair, especially when you are just a student, would not only provide a “source of stress” but also cause a disturbance. Having a romantic relationship is really disturbing because a student will deal with managing time between school and the romantic side, which somehow leads to giving academic work a lower priority. Stress is a continuous feeling of worry about work or personal life that prevents someone from relaxing. Campbell, as cited by Crissey (2006), pointed out that stress is a condition or effect that is bad and can cause some problems. For example, students who are having any romantic affair will have a higher percentage of stress than those who don't have because instead of focusing on their academic work and academic stressors, they also spend most of their time on their relationships. After all, Einstein did say, “Love is a better teacher than duty.” An article by Lockwood, 2017 talked about love and other grades: A study of the effects of romantic relationship status on the academic performance of university students; among the few studies that have examined the effects of romantic relationships on academic performance, most have been concerned with adolescent students. This study analyzes a data set of more than 300 students at a

mid-sized, private university in the northeastern United States to determine whether participating in a romantic relationship predicts grade point average or course attendance. The results of multivariate analyses indicate that being in a romantic relationship while in college is significantly associated with class absences but not with grade point average. Specifically, logistic regression models show that participation in a romantic relationship more than doubles the odds of failing to attend three or more class meetings per course in a semester. The practical implication of this finding is the consideration of romantic relationships among the undergraduate student body by university administrators and faculty when attempting to address course attendance concerns. Additionally, this study suggests that future researchers examine the characteristics of romantic relationships and romantic partners in order to fully understand how such relationships might affect the academic performance of university students.

In a research paper written by Joshua Elevate 2016, he stated that early romantic relationship has advantages as well as disadvantages. First, many teenagers excel in their class because they become motivated to study hard due to their partner, which is considered a positive result for every student and for teenagers who have an early romantic relationship. The second advantage is that many teenagers “get inspired” because their partners give them inspiration for so many things. The third advantage is that many are “happy to have a partner” because their relationship gives them joy and happiness. Many teenagers look for a partner that gives them joy and contentment. The fourth advantage is that many students and teenagers “gain better self-esteem or self-confidence.” Many teenagers who have early romantic relationships gain self-confidence because when they have a partner, they feel safe and secure. Our partnership gives us assurance; our partner gives us assurance that we can do more.

Lastly, many teenagers said that “they gain more friends” as a result of their partners. When we are in a relationship, we encounter and meet our boyfriends’ or girlfriends’ friends. There are more advantages to having an early romantic relationship. These are the positive results for every teenager who is engaged in romantic relationships. It is to know that having an early romantic relationship gives them positive results in every aspect of their lives, including their social and emotional life. Most teenagers and students answered that one of the disadvantages of having an early romantic relationship and how it affects their study is that “they gain lower grades” because of their boyfriends or girlfriends. The disadvantage for many teenagers is that they learn to keep secrets from their parents. Third, teens tend to be quarrelsome. Both men and women today just become quarrelsome because of their partners; a sort of “mind your own and stay away from what is mine” audacity of a teenager. The fourth disadvantage is that many teens come home late because they want to spend more time with their partners. Lastly, having an early romantic relationship causes them to disregard major priorities. They want to give more attention and time to their boyfriends or girlfriends. The reason why teens forget to prioritize combat focus and manage more important things. This disadvantage is only a few from many disadvantages and negative effects of teenagers engaging in an early romantic relationship. The result of the study of Phelps (2007) implies that factors presumed to affect students’ academic performance, such as personal relationships, vary in each race. Since we have known that teachers in UP Cebu have higher expectations of their students, increased workloads, challenging exercises, projects, and assignments are given to the students. This notion is also supported by Manning, Giordano, Longmore, & Hocevar (Cui & Fincham, 2011) who stated that college is the time when studies are more stressful than before. We cannot say that early romantic relationships are

right or wrong; we cannot criticize or judge what teenagers do; there is nothing wrong to try and enter a romantic relationship. As Domenico Cieri Estrada would say, “To know when to go away and when to come closer is the key to any lasting relationship.” It only becomes wrong in how you handle your relationship with someone.

Significance of the Study. This study highlights the effect of time management and motivation on students who are involved in romantic relationships. The results of this study would alert the twelfth graders in Dakar and raise their awareness of the effects of romantic relationships on the academic performance of students, especially their negative effects. The data would also help these twelfth graders who are involved in romantic relationships assess their time management between romantic and academic aspects. The findings of this study would also raise the awareness of the parents of these twelve graders who are balancing their time between academic work and romantic aspects. These findings could benefit them so that they can guide their children on how to balance their time wisely; as parents, they are tasked with motivating their children to prioritize their studies and to set aside or minimize factors of romantic relationships (i.e., more frequent interaction with the partner) that can affect their children’s academic performance of their children. For the teachers, the information that I obtain from this study will help them understand that this issue plays a big part or serves as a major factor in whether twelfth graders get low or high grades in school. It will also help them be aware and open-minded about this issue by helping in increasing the academic performance of their students, not only by teaching them the lessons in the courses or subjects they handle.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

I implemented a simple descriptive and exploratory design. This design used survey questionnaires that were distributed to the twelfth graders specifically to attain the main objective of the study, which is to examine the effects of romantic relationships on twelve graders' academic performance in Dakar. The research itself tried to describe, analyze, and interpret the status of the students. The design is a non-experimental case-study correlation research. This design investigated the relationship between the variables without manipulating them. The two main variables evaluated were academic performance and romantic relationships, which involve time management and levels of motivation.

Participants and Locale of the Study. The research was conducted online, using constructed surveys for twelfth graders in Dakar during the first, second, and third semesters of the 2019-2020 academic year, regardless of gender and the type of high school in Dakar. There were twenty-nine respondents who took part in the study. The population consisted of twelfth graders in Dakar who participated on a strictly voluntary basis.

Sampling Procedure. The researcher made use of the selective sampling method in the selection of the twelfth graders since the study was focused on a particular group (students involved in romantic relationships). Twelfth graders

in Dakar in the A.Y. 2019-2020 became the participants of the study. There were only twelve students who met these criteria. Thirty students were the respondents of the study.

Data collection. The gathering of data for this study utilized a self-administered descriptive questionnaire because it economizes time and effort and has the ability to maintain confidentiality. The participants will be requested to voluntarily complete the survey questionnaires online to provide the necessary data for the study. After gathering the data, the researcher will group the responses according to the sub-problems of the study.

Instrumentation. In order to answer specific sub-problems in this study, survey questionnaires will be distributed to the twelfth graders in Dakar. Interviews with some of the students will also be conducted to confirm the results of the survey. The survey questionnaires will consist of a broad range of questions aimed at gauging the students' involvement in romantic relationships and their adverse effects on their academic achievement. Each questionnaire will have three parts. The first part of the questionnaire will cover the profile of the respondent (i.e., name, gender, etc.). The second part will comprise the status of time management of the student. The third and fourth parts will consider the levels of motivation of the student as twelfth graders in Dakar. These two last parts are in a Likert scale format in which respondents will be tasked to indicate whether they strongly agree, agree, are undecided, disagree, or strongly disagree with the given statements.

Statistical treatment of data. Data that will be collected will be converted to a percentage and presented in tabular and graphical forms for simple interpretation.

1. To determine the profile of the respondents in terms of gender and grade average, the percentage will be used: Formula:

$$p = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where: P= Percentage, F= Frequency, N= No. of respondents.

2. To determine the status of time management and the level of motivation,

the weighted mean will be used. Formula: $\bar{X} =$

$$\frac{\sum f(x)}{N}$$

Where: \bar{X} = mean, $\sum(x)$ = total scores of students, N = No. of respondents.

3. To determine the significant correlation between academic performance and time management; levels of motivation and academic performance, the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation (r) and the t-test will be used. Formulas: (Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation)

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where: r = the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation; n = sample size; $\sum x$ = summation of x; $\sum y$ = summation of y; $\sum x^2$ = sum of squares of x; $\sum y^2$ = sum of squares of y.

(T-test)

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n - 2}{1 - r^2}}$$

Where: t = computed table value; r = the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation; N = number of respondents.

CHAPTER V

PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter presents the data gathered, which comprised an electronic consent in Part One. The second part comprised the profile of students in terms of gender, religion, age, parents' marital status,, housing status as well as relationship status. The third part the survey comprised of the general weighted average in the academic year 2019-2020, the status of time management in studying and with the partner, and the levels of motivation of the respondents as a student. In order to answer the main problem of the study which is to determine the effects of romantic relationships on the academic performance of twelfth-grade students (A.Y.2019-2020), the data gathered were then tallied and presented in tabulated and textual form, analyzed using the statistical formula described in the previous chapter, and interpreted according to the sub-problems of the study.

B. Respondent's Profile - The profile of the respondents was determined by their gender, age, religion, parents's marital status,, living status as well as

relationship status which were indicated in the second part of the survey after the confirmation of the electronic consent available in the first part of (the survey. Most of the respondents were female because the majority of the twelfth-grade students who were involved in a romantic relationship were female. Figure 1.1 shows the distribution of respondents by gender. There are eight (28.6%) male respondents and twenty (71.4%) female respondents.

The respondents' general average in the Academic Year 2020-2021 was also used to measure their academic performance before, during, and after their relationships. Considering the differences in mental capabilities of the respondents, academic performance was measured

according to the number of points that had changed in their average from the first to the second semester, before, during, and after the end of their relationships. Data show that 58.3% of the respondents scored above average (80-70), 8.3% of the respondents scored excellent (100- 90), and 33.3% of the respondents also scored average (60-50) in their academic performance before the start of their relationship. 58.3% (80-70) scored above average, 8.3 (100-90) scored excellent, 25% (60-50) scored average, and 8.3% (40-30) scored below average. After their relationships, 66.7 (80-70) scored above average, 25% (60-50) scored average, and 8.3% (100-90) scored excellent after the end of their relationships. Table 1 shows the academic performance of the respondents in the first and second semester of Academic Year 2019-2020. The scores in academic performance were not indicated.

Table 1 – Respondents’ Profile in Terms of GWA in the A.Y. 2019 – 2020

Student	Academic Performance in 1 st Semester			Academic Performance in 2 nd Semester		
	Before	During	After	Before	During	After
A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A
B	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A
C	A	A.A	A.A	N/A	N/A	N/A
D	E	E	E	N/A	E	E
E	A.A	A	N/A	A.A	A	A.A
F	A.A	A.A	N/A	N/A	A.A	N/A
G	A.A	A	A	N/A	A	N/A
H	A	A.A	N/A	N/A	A.A	N/A
I	A.A	A.A	N/A	N/A	A.A	A.A
J	A.A	A	A	A.A	A	A
K	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A	A.A
L	A	B.A	N/A	N/A	B.A	A

Legend:

A.A = Above Average (80-70) A = Average (60-50) E = Excellent (100-90) B.A = Below Average (40-30) and N/A = Not Applicable (if the relationship ended at that time or progressed past that time, which do not correspond)

There are six (50%) respondents whose academic performance remained the same from the first to the second semester; three (25%) have increased, and three (25%) decreased from the first to the second semester. It entails that most of the respondents have average performance was maintained on the second semester performance. Most students were involved in a romantic relationship twice since the beginning, starting from after the end of their relationship. It then follows that very of the respondents have lowered academic their senior year, which included the first relationship that started first semester and ended first semester. This is why there is an averaged score available for before, during, and after the end of their relationship for the first semester, and marked Not Applicable for after the end of their relationship for the first semester, as well as before the relationship started for the second semester if the first relationship continued into the second semester, or if the second relationship started second semester and ended second semester, or is still in progress. This is why there is also data for their average scores before, during, and after the end of their relationship if it ended second semester, and marked Not Applicable for after the end of their relationship if the second relationship is still in progress. Some students' relationship continued from the first semester into the second semester, where it ended or is still current. Few relationships had only one relationship, which started and ended within the first semester; therefore, their academic performance for the second semester, before, during, and after the end of their relationship, was marked as not applicable because they were not involved in any romantic relationship during the second semester. Additionally, the data gathered needs to

show a relationship between the time of their relationship and their averaged scores. The next part of this chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered, which are the respondents' answers on the survey questionnaire. Statistical formulas, such as the weighted mean, Pearson product-moment correlation, and the t-test of Pearson's significance, were used to get their overall response of the respondents to the survey questions and to test for significant correlations between the variables.

2. Status of Time Management

According to Crissey (2006), teenagers who engage in romantic relationships are often challenged in balancing the relationship and academics. She added that this challenge creates pressure on how to maintain the romantic side and academic work at the same time. On the other hand, Myers (2010) stated that for college students, romantic relationships consume a lot of time. This implies that the time they must spend a lot in studying is consumed by spending time with their partner. The respondents' answers were classified as 1-2hrs/week, 2-3hrs/week, and 3-4hrs/week, 4-5hrs/week and more than 5hrs/week.

Data reveal that most respondents maintained their 2-3hrs/week in time to study before, during, and after the end of the relationship. Meanwhile, seven (58.4%) respondents answered that they spent 2-3hrs/day studying, 1(8.3%) 3-4hrs/day, 2(16.6%) 4-5hrs/day, 3 (25%) 1-2hrs/day and 2(16.7%) more than 5hrs. /day during their relationship. Five (41.6%) responded that they spent 2-3hrs. /day for studying, 1(8.3%) 3-4hrs/day, 2(16.6%) 4-5hrs/day, 3 (25%) 1-2hrs/day and 3(25%) more than 5hrs. /day before the start of their relationship. Four (33.3%) responded that they spent 2-3hrs. /day for studying, 2(16.6%) 3-4hrs/day,

1(8.3%) 4-5hrs/day and 3(25%) more than 5hrs. /day after the end of their relationship. The weighted count (7 - which implies more in this case) of the time spent studying is more compared to the weighted count (1- which means less in this case) of the time spent studying before, during, and after the end of their relationship. It implies that the respondents spend more time with their partner than in studying. The results support Crissey's argument that the respondents' status of time management is not balanced because they spent more time with their partner than in studying. It also implies that the students were more focused on their romantic relationship than on their academic work. It further supports the researchers' proposition in the study:the more time a person spends in her Social Exchange theory, people who are involved in a romantic relationship interact, and the less time will remain for other tasks. Furthermore, according to Wang (2004) in with each other in order to maintain the relationship and have a feeling of being loved and cared for. This situation, however, affects other tasks of persons involved because they provide rewards for one another (which is the time with each other) and these rewards that they give would also become a cost which means that they have lost their time that must be allotted for some important matters such as academic work.

3. Levels of Motivation as a Student

Davis (1999) said that there are students who seem to be passionate about learning, but others also need inspiration in order to be stimulated. She suggested that students should be given their needs such as the need to be involved or in other words, the need to belong. "Motivation is the force that drives a person to do something" (Sweetland, n.d.). According to the Need to Belong theory, a person is motivated to do tasks when he/she satisfies the need to belong in a relationship. Having a partner makes an individual feel affection, care, and the like, that makes them motivated. In addition, the review of related studies described that there is,

somehow, a sense of motivation among students who are involved in romantic relationships, which made them perform better in their academics. Additionally, Crissey (2006) inspires the students involved. Furthermore, motivation allows students to give their best on said that one beneficial effect of a romantic relationship on academic performance is that it gives students the task provided. Table 2 shows the perception of the respondents on their levels of motivation as a student while they are involved in a romantic relationship. The weighted mean in each item was computed to find the general perception of the respondents on their levels of motivation as a student.

ITEM	CHOICES										Overall Perception on the item	
	SA		A		N		SD		D		WM	Description
	f	w	f	w	f	w	f	w	f	w		
Do/did you find yourself competing with your partner all the time?	0	0	0	0	2	16.7	6	50	4	33.3	4.7	A
I feel/felt that I would do anything for my partner	1	8.3	5	41.7	6	50	0	0	0	0	5.2	A
My partner inspires/inspired me to study	5	41.7	0	0	2	16.7	2	16.7	3	25	3.5	N
My boyfriend/girlfriend was/is very ambitious	3	25	4	33.3	3	25	0	0	2	16.7	3.2	N
My boyfriend/girlfriend is/was very determined in terms of education	4	33.3	4	33.3	2	16.7	0	0	2	16.7	3.3	N
Overall Perceptions on the level of motivation	13	108.3	13	108.3	15	125.1	8	66.7	11	91.7	12.2	A

Legend:

SA –Strongly Agree U–Undecided SD –Strongly Disagree WM– Weighted Mean
 f – frequency A – Agree D–Disagree W –Weight

The results reveal that the respondents' level of motivation as a student is neutral, as is evident in a weighted mean of (4.7). It means that their involvement in a romantic

relationship has a neutral effect on the respondents' motivation as students. This means that even though there is some motivation for the students when they are involved in a romantic relationship, it has only a minimal impact on their part in playing their role as students. The statement "I feel/felt that I would do anything for my partner" got the highest weighted mean of 5.2 (Agree). One (8.3%) respondent strongly agreed with the statement; five (41.7%) respondents agreed; two (16.7%) respondents were neutral; zero (0%) respondents disagreed; and still zero (0%) respondents strongly disagreed. It entails that the majority of respondents agreed that they feel/felt that they would do anything for their partner, which is in line with the perspective of Lucas & Curpuz (2007) saying that romantic relationships offer a positive environment for learning because they provide stability, trust, and care to the students involved.

Students tend to get involved in a romantic relationship because it makes them feel more knowledgeable and motivated to be with a person who can complement their needs to whom they can share their problems. Moreover, finding a person whom they can lean on would also lessen the burdens that they carry in their lives. This is why they feel more motivated when they have romantic partners. In the meantime, other factors of romantic relationship described by the statements in the questionnaire don't really affect their motivation as students.

4. Correlation of Time Management and Academic Performance

As shown in the previous pages, the respondents became more focused on their romantic relationship since they spend more time with their partner than in studying. The students who are involved in a relationship have faced a challenge in balancing their time in academics and

romantic lives. Consequently, it is indeed important to find out if there is a correlation between the respondents' time management and their academic performance. In finding the correlation between time management and academic performance, it will be divided into two categories: time spent studying versus academic performance, and time spent with their partner versus academic performance. Crissey (2006) who studied the impact of romantic relationships among girls in high school, believed that the time management of students involved in romantic relationships affects their academic performance. She said that the more time spent by the students to their partner, the less time they will spend studying. Consequently, the present study investigates whether there is a significant relationship between time management (which constitutes the time the respondents spend studying and with their partner) and the academic performance of students in a romantic relationship. Table 3 illustrates the correlation between time spent studying and academic performance.

Student	Time Spent Studying/day			Average scores in Academic Performance		
	Before	During	After	Before	During	After
A	4-5hrs	4-5hrs	3-4hrs	A.A	A.A	A.A
B	2-3hrs	2-3hrs	2-3hrs	A.A	A.A	A.A
C	1-2hrs	1-2hrs	1-2hrs	A	A.A	A.A
D	4-5hrs	4-5hrs	>5hrs	E	E	E
E	2-3hrs	2-3hrs	2-3hrs	A.A	A	A.A
F	1-2hrs	1-2hrs	1-2hrs	A.A	A.A	A.A
G	>5hrs	>5hrs	>5hrs	A.A	A	A
H	>5hrs	2-3hrs	4-5hrs	A	A.A	A.A
I	>5hrs	>5hrs	>5hrs	A.A	A.A	A.A
J	1-2hrs	2-3hrs	2-3hrs	A	A	A
K	2-4hrs	2-4hrs	2-4hrs	A.A	A.A	A.A
L	2-3hrs	1-2hrs	1-2hrs	A	B.A	A

Legend:

A.A = Above Average (80-70) A = Average (60-50) E = Excellent (100-90) B.A = Below Average (40-30)

Data show that there is a slight relationship between the two variables mentioned earlier. It suggests that the amount of time they spend studying does not necessarily affect their academic performance. This is due to the fact that there are still other academic works that the students may have done in order to succeed in academics, such as making projects and assignments. On the other hand, Crissey (2006) also proposed that the students' time spent with their partner affects their academic performance. This is supported by social exchange theory, which proposed that rewards given to the partner, such as time, would imply a cost for the giver since this source, which must be needed to accomplish other important tasks such as doing schoolwork, is lost. Table 4 illustrates the correlation between time spent with partner and the academic performance of the respondents.

Student	Time Spent with Partner	Average Academic Scores
A	Rarely = 2	Above Average
B	Almost Always = 4	Above Average
C	Rarely = 2	Above Average
D	Rarely = 2	Excellent
E	Rarely = 2	Average
F	Rarely = 2	Above Average
G	Always = 5	Average
H	Almost Always = 4	Above Average
I	Sometimes = 3	Above Average
J	Rarely = 2	Average
K	Sometimes = 3	Above Average
L	Always = 5	Below Average

Table 4 shows that the student with the most time spent with the partner has the least score in academic performance. Additionally, in the interviews conducted by the researcher, the results reveal that the respondents were more pressured in managing their time the moment their romantic partners called or wanted to communicate with them, since they were given

Table 5 shows that there is no significant relationship between the levels of motivation of the respondents as students and their academic performance. Meaning to say, a higher level of motivation among the respondents as students, when it relates to their romantic relationship, does not necessarily imply that their academic performance will also be higher. The data presented in Table 5 implies that the respondents' level of motivation shows a very low coefficient of correlation. Meaning to say, the change in the grades of the respondents was not dependent on their level of motivation. Respondents' perceptions of their levels of motivation as students while in a romantic relationship do not show any pattern of relationship between levels of motivation and academic performance. One of the respondents said, "Even though a romantic relationship offers motivation as well as inspiration, misunderstandings and conflicts can't still be avoided; that is why motivation doesn't really give impact to academic performance". Same is true with another respondent who said, "It is true that romantic relationship allows me to motivate myself to study well, but there is still some time that comes that it disappointed me because my partner doesn't respond to my messages and he often said that he is busy or tired whenever I want to talk with him after a fight, that is why I broke up with him." These statements given by the respondents indicate that motivation doesn't have an impact on their academic performance because there are situations in a romantic relationship that would oppose the purpose of motivation. It implies that there are factors in a romantic relationship that give more impact on the academic performance of the students rather than the motivation it gives to the students.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS - The study aimed to determine the effects of romantic relationship on the academic performance of the twelfth graders in Dakar. Data needed are

gathered through an online survey platform from the students of the sample population who were involved in a romantic relationship during the academic year 2019-2020 in order to attain the objectives. The summary of findings is as follows:

1. The results indicate that the majority of the twelfth graders who were involved in a romantic relationship have maintained their general weighted average from the first semester to the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020.
2. The results show that the respondents spent more time with their partner than in studying. This is evident in their weighted mean. The time spent in studying obtained a weighted mean of 3 (Sometimes) while the time spent with their partner obtained a weighted mean of 6 (Almost Always).
3. The results reveal that the respondents' level of motivation as students, considering their involvement in a romantic relationship, is neutral. This is evident in the results from the table.
4. The results suggest that there is a positive correlation between the time spent in studying and academic performance, but it is not statistically significant. Meaning to say, although there is a slight relationship between academic performance and the time spent in studying, there is not enough statistical evidence in the data showing that academic performance depends on the time spent in studying.

5. The results denote that there is a significant negative correlation between time spent with the partner and the academic performance of the twelfth graders who were involved in romantic relationships. Findings indicate that the more time the respondents spent with their partner, decrease in academic performance that followed. Moreover, the data gathered from the interviews also supported the results. The respondents were more pressured in managing their time the moment their romantic partner called or wanted to communicate with them. They showed that their romantic partners were given priority instead of studying, making projects, or completing assignments and the like, thus making the academic performance be affected.

6. The results depict that the correlation between the respondents' level of motivation and academic performance is very low. Meaning to say, the respondents' change in the grades of the respondents was not dependent on their level of motivation. That can be deduced from the data wherein a respondent who had score of 3.6 in the level of motivation has a positive score in academic performance, while another respondent who is in the same level of motivation has a negative score in academic performance.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on results of the study, it was found that there is a significant effect of romantic relationships on the academic performance of the twelfth graders in Dakar.

Adolescent stage is the stage when people begin looking for romantic partners. For twelfth graders in Dakar who are involved in romantic relationships, it can be noticed that they are more focused on their romantic relationship. They were not able to

balance their time between romantic relationships and academics. Since high school is not easy due to increase in workloads and the greater responsibilities given to the students, students who spend more time with their partners have lower academic performance.

In conclusion, if students are involved in a romantic relationship, a higher level of anxiety that the students would experience in a romantic relationship would indicate a great possibility that it would offer negative effects to their academic performance.

Yet twelfth graders who are involved in a romantic relationship have reported that they have a low level of anxiety. It can be implied that there is no other factor that greatly affects the negative academic performance of twelfth graders but the time they spend with their partner. Conversely, the

Researcher found out that the respondents' level of motivation as students has only a slight relationship with academic performance, which implies that it doesn't necessarily affect academic performance as much as the time spent with their partner does.

RECOMMENDATIONS. This study covers only a small part of the population of twelfth graders who are involved in romantic relationship with which the researcher cannot generalize the findings for all adolescents who are involved in romantic relationships. Thus, for the researcher(s) who will be going to research more about the effects of romantic relationship in the academic performance of the student, we highly recommend that they must gather respondents from a wider range, since this study is focused only on the views of 12 respondents from twelfth-grade students in Dakar. Moreover, limited respondents may affect the precision of the study's results of the

study. For twelfth graders, the researcher recommends that if they involve themselves in a romantic relationship, they must balance their time management in order not to affect their academic performance. In addition, for students who are involved in a relationship and for those who are planning to be involved, I recommend that they should be aware of the anxieties that romantic relationships would bring so that they could manage themselves and cope with the problems that would arise in this relationship. It is also recommended that parents should not encourage their kids to be involved in a romantic relationship, since it contributes to the decline in their academic performance, even though it also encourages the development of adolescents for a better committed relationship in the future. However, together with this, there must be guidance that the academic performance of their kids will not be affected.

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